

38, 228) have isolated a similar pyridine base from coal tar and have recorded its boiling point as 173-74°/734 mm. and the m. p. of its picrate as 143-44°. The picrate of this product also melted at 144°. (Found: N, 16.10. $C_{14}H_{14}O_7N_4$ requires N, 16.0 per cent).

In conclusion we wish to express our sincere thanks to Professor Dr. H. K. Sen, for placing the resources of his laboratory at our disposal.

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The Coagulation of Ferrocyanide Sols containing Varying Amounts of Potassium Ferrocyanide.

BY NIRMALAPADA CHATTERJEE.

The part played by the adsorption of constituent ions in determining the electrical charge of inorganic colloids is fairly understood. The relationship observed by Lottermoser (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1908, 62, 372) between the excess of the constituent ions present during the precipitation of similar halides and the sign of their charge find a simple explanation from the theoretical considerations of Mukherjee (*Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1921, 16, 103) who pointed out the importance of the lattice forces in determining the nature of the primarily adsorbed layer on the surface. The electro-osmotic observations of Mukherjee and co-workers (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1924 31, 178; 1926, 3, 335, 371; 1927, 4, 459) support the theoretical considerations. The relative adsorbabilities of such ions have been discussed by them with reference to barium sulphate, lead chromate and silver halides. It has been found that associated with the primarily adsorbed layer there is often present a secondary adsorption of hydrogen and hydroxyl ions which lead respectively to the liberation of alkali and acid from the double decomposition of the reacting neutral salts. With increasing concentration of adsorbable ions having the same sign of charge as the surface, frequently the electrical charge increases to a maximum and then diminishes. In conformity to this, the stability of the colloidal solution under such conditions as measured by the coagulating concentrations of an electrolyte has also often been found to pass through a maximum. The stability of a sol and

the cataphoretic velocity of its particles are, however, not directly related (*cf.* Mukherjee and co-workers, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1927, **4**, 493).

Neidle (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1917, **39**, 2334) as also Sen (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1925, **29**, 517) observed in the case of ferric hydroxide sol that in presence of an increasing concentration of hydrochloric acid, the stability towards potassium sulphate passes through a maximum. The primary adsorption of hydrogen ions on ferric hydroxide sol is quite strong but at high concentrations of hydrochloric acid, the electrical adsorption of chlorine ions may predominate. Sen (*loc. cit.*) and Weiser (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1926, **30**, 20) studied the stabilising effect of the constituent ions, *e.g.*, ferrocyanide ion on Prussian blue and copper ferrocyanide sol. With the progressive addition of potassium ferrocyanide, the stability towards potassium sulphate or chloride shows a similar maximum.

In the calculation of the coagulating value of an ion when mixtures of electrolytes are used, very often the total amount of the coagulating ions present in the system is not considered. From the results obtained by Sen (*loc. cit.*) and Weiser (*loc. cit.*) on the coagulating effect of potassium chloride on copper ferrocyanide sol, containing increasing amounts of potassium ferrocyanide it would appear that if the total concentration of potassium ions be taken into consideration, the coagulating value does not reach a maximum but increases continually. It was, therefore, thought desirable to test their point.

Dilution of a sol is known to affect the coagulating concentration of an electrolyte in several ways. It decreases the concentration of the particles and therefore the colloid-liquid interface decreases and also the distance between the particles increases. Mukherjee and Sen (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1919, **115**, 461), as also Kruyt and Spek (*Kolloid Z.*, 1919, **25**, 1), pointed out that the decrease of the colloid-liquid interface increased the adsorption of an electrolyte per unit area of the surface and this would sensitise the sol. This effect would be negligible when monovalent precipitating ions are considered because the concentration of the electrolyte is high. On the other hand, the increased distance stabilises the sol by lessening the collisions between particles. The resultant effect of the two will decide whether the sol is stabilised or sensitised on dilution. When a sol containing an appreciable amount of the stabilising electrolyte is diluted, the concentration of the electrolyte diminishes but even

with the same colloidal substance both a sensitisation and a stabilisation has been observed. Weiser and Nicholas (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 25, 742) and Ghosh and Dhar (*ibid.*, 1925, 29, 159), determined the coagulating concentration of potassium chloride on different dilutions of Prussian blue sol. Weiser and Nicholas worked with a sol which contained considerable amount of potassium ferrocyanide and found that the sol became unstable on dilution. The sol used by Ghosh and Dhar was almost free from potassium ferrocyanide and a stabilisation was observed. In order to verify whether Weiser and Nicholas's contradictory observations were due to the presence of potassium ferrocyanide, Ghosh and Dhar (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1927, 31, 187) added to the sol considerable amount of the salt but they did not find any sensitisation.

In a previous paper (Chatterjee, *Kolloid Z.*, 1930, 52, 214) the following results were obtained. (a) For uranium ferrocyanide sol containing additions of potassium ferrocyanide in concentrations proportionate to the dilution, the total amount of potassium ions necessary for coagulation with potassium chloride decreases with the dilution. (b) If the strength of free potassium ferrocyanide (0.005*N*) was kept constant for all the dilutions, the coagulating concentration decreased on dilution of the sol but the difference observed under (a) markedly diminishes and with thorium chloride, instead of a decrease an increase in the coagulating concentration occurred. (c) When a fixed amount of a strong solution of potassium ferrocyanide was added to the same volume of all the dilutions, coagulation with potassium chloride shows stabilisation on dilution.

In the present work the same amount of potassium ferrocyanide was added to the dilutions of a number of ferrocyanide sols. The amount of the salt was gradually increased and the concentration of potassium chloride necessary to coagulate the sols were determined. The total concentration of cations is taken as a measure of the stability of the sol. The cations *being* the same in both the electrolytes, the antagonistic effect is absent. The coagulating concentrations of different electrolytes for the concentrated and dilute sols in absence of the added potassium ferrocyanide, were also determined.

By the usual method of preparation of ferrocyanide sols, the intermicellary liquid contains some amount of potassium ferrocyanide. Sols used in the present work were at first precipitated from an excess of the metallic salts and then the precipitate was centrifuged. The supernatant liquid was thrown away and fresh water was added

and the sol was centrifuged again. The process was repeated till peptisation occurred. The concentration of free electrolytes in the intercellary liquid was thus considerably reduced.

The cataphoretic velocity was measured for the concentrated and the diluted sol of copper ferrocyanide containing the same amounts of potassium ferrocyanide solution. The p_H values of the ultrafiltrate of the above mixtures were also determined colorimetrically. Specific conductivities of the sols were also measured.

Preparation of sols.—A slight excess of an approximately normal solution of the chloride of the metal was mixed with a solution of potassium ferrocyanide of equivalent strength. In the case of uranyl ferrocyanide, the nitrate was used. The precipitates were washed and centrifuged; the supernatant liquid was discarded and the process repeated. The p_H value and specific conductivity of the supernatant liquids were determined. The ions present were also tested. After several washings in this way, the substance was peptised. The sols of Prussian blue, uranyl ferrocyanide and aluminium ferrocyanide had an acid while copper, zinc and cadmium ferrocyanide had an alkaline reaction.

The coagulating concentrations were determined in the previous paper (Chatterjee, *loc. cit.*) in the manner described by Mukherjee and Ghosh (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 1, 213). The coagulating concentration was determined in the present case differently. After adding the coagulating electrolyte to both dilutions of the sol, the sols were centrifuged for 8 minutes. The minimum concentration necessary for producing a clear supernatant liquid was taken as the equicoagulating concentration of an electrolyte.

In the following series, the coagulating concentrations of electrolytes for the sols and their dilution are given. Column (I) indicates the coagulating concentrations of electrolytes expressed in milliequivalents per litre. Column (II) indicates the activity of the coagulating concentrations of cations, calculated for the very dilute solutions, multiplied by 1000. For univalent electrolytes, the simplified equation of Debye and Hückel has been used (Brönsted, *Trans. Faraday Soc.*, 1927, 33, 416).

$$\log \gamma = \frac{-0.5\sqrt{\mu}}{1 + A\sqrt{\mu}}$$

Where γ denotes the activity coefficient of the ion; μ , the ionic strength of the electrolyte; A , a const. = 1.65 from Scatchard's data.

For electrolytes having ions of higher valency where $\sqrt{\mu}$ is less than 0.1, the following equation has been used :

$\text{Log } \gamma = 0.5 Z^2 \sqrt{\mu}$, where Z is the valency of the ion.

The activity coefficients are only approximate specially at high concentrations. The activity coefficients, therefore, at high concentrations are not given in the tables.

Coagulating Concentration of Different Electrolytes on Ferrocyanide Sols and their Dilutions when no Potassium Ferrocyanide is Added.

TABLE I.

Uranium ferrocyanide sol.

Sol.	KNO ₃		AlCl ₃		ThCl ₄		K ₃ Fe(CN) ₆
	I	II	I	II	I	II	
A	9	8.08	0.14	0.104	0.052	0.035	150
A/2	15	13.36	0.101	0.078	0.04	0.028	240
A/4	+20	17.58	-0.083	0.066			+306

TABLE II.

Prussian blue sol.

Sol	K ₄ Fe(CN) ₆	KCl		AgNO ₃		BaCl ₂		AlCl ₃		ThCl ₄	
		I	II	I	II	I	II	I	II	I	II
A	280	10	9.08	0.375	0.368	1.5	1.01	0.08	0.064	0.014	0.012
A/2	+300	+17.5	15.48	-0.300	0.294	+2	+1.41	-0.066	0.054	-0.0099	0.0083

The preceding tables show the usual behaviour on dilution (Mukherjee and Sen *loc. cit.*) namely the dilute sol requires higher concentration when the coagulating ion is univalent and a smaller one when these ions are polyvalent. Barium resembles a univalent ion in this respect. Silver ions resemble on the other hand the polyvalent ions in agreement with previous observation and with its known greater absorbability. The two factors—the stabilising effect produced by the diminution in the number of collisions, and the sensitising effect of the greater adsorption per unit surface of the more dilute sol (which would be more prominent for ions having a low

* indicates a stabilisation on dilution,—a sensitisation and 0, neither stabilisation nor sensitisation.

coagulating concentration), are sufficient to account for the preceding observations. The coagulating concentration of potassium ferrocyanide is much larger than those of the nitrate or chloride in agreement with the expected greater adsorption of the constituent ferrocyanide ion. Table III shows that this is true of the other ferrocyanide sols. The differences in the coagulating concentration of potassium chloride for the two dilutions may be very small. For copper ferrocyanide, the two dilutions are coagulated at the same concentration. The addition of potassium ferrocyanide in small concentrations systematically increases the coagulating concentration of potassium ions. The dilute sol should therefore be less stable as the concentration of the free ferrocyanide would diminish on dilution. The stabilising effect of the greater distance between the particles on dilution, therefore, appears to be the predominating factor.

TABLE III.

Sol	$\text{Cu}_2\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$ Sol		$\text{Zn}_2\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$ Sol	$\text{Cd}_2\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$ Sol		$\text{Al}_4[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]_3$ Sol					
	KCl		$\text{K}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$	KCl		KCl		$\text{K}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$	KCl		$\text{K}_4\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6$
	I	II		I	II	I	II		I	II	
A	19.2	16.9	400	2.6	2.45	5	4.62	848	5	4.62	250
A/2	19.2	16.9	+440	+2.9	2.73	+7.5	6.8	+900	+7.5	6.8	+300

In the previous paper (Chatterjee, *loc. cit.*) a sensitisation on dilution was observed against potassium chloride and nitrate in the case of uranium ferrocyanide sol which contained an appreciable amount of potassium ferrocyanide. As will be shown later the amount of the stabilising electrolyte, possibly also the number and size of the particles, influence the behaviour of the sol on dilution. Apart from the differences in these respects, the uranium ferrocyanide sol used in the earlier case contained some free potassium nitrate. Potassium nitrate was, therefore, added in amounts proportional to the dilution to the sol used in this work. The results are given in Table IV.

TABLE IV.

Sol.	KNO_3 added.	Coagulating conc. of electrolytes in m. equiv./litre.		
		KNO_3 .	AlCl_3 .	ThCl_4 .
A	2 m. equiv./litre.	6.5	0.072	0.021
A/2	1	+12.5	-0.063	+0.023

With proportionate decrease of the amount of potassium nitrate added to the sols A and A/2, a stabilisation against thorium chloride, as observed previously, is again observed. The degree of sensitisation as measured by the percentage change in the coagulating concentration also diminishes for the other electrolytes. The coagulating concentrations measured by the method used in the present and that used in the earlier work show the same manner of variations with dilution.

The coagulating concentrations of potassium chloride were determined for two dilutions of each sol both containing the same amounts of potassium ferrocyanide. The amount of free potassium ferrocyanide in the sol is negligible in comparison with the amount added.

Columns (I) and (II) give as before the coagulating concentrations and activities respectively of the total number of cations of the added electrolytes.

TABLE V.

Conc. of $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ added are given in m. equiv. per litre.

Uranium ferrocyanide sol.

Sol.	$K_4Fe(CN)_6$ added to sol.				$K_4Fe(CN)_6$ added to sol.						
	0.05		0.2	2.0	4.0	25	50	100	250	750	1000
	I	II	I	I	I	I	I	I	I	I	I
A	21	18.5	157.2	352		810	920	1000	1210	1535	1700
A/2	+52	43.2	+175.2	352	+441	-725					-1525

Prussian blue sol.

Sol.	$K_4Fe(CN)_6$ added to sol.						
	0.025		0.05	0.25	0.5	25	50
	I	I	I	I	I	I	I
A			70		357.5	207	2.4
A/2	87.5		+105	367.2	-350.5	-200	

Copper ferrocyanide sol.

Sol.	$K_4Fe(CN)_6$ added.		
	0.10		100
	I	II	I
A	28	24.2	250
A/2	+29.4	25.3	-235

Zinc ferrocyanide sol.

Sol.	$K_4Fe(CN)_6$ added.			
	0.10		50	200
	I	II	I	I
A	3.5	3.36	330	1075
A/2	+4.37	4.14	+347	+1110

Cadmium ferrocyanide sol.

Sol.	$K_4Fe(CN)_6$ added.		
	0.10		200
	I	II	I
A	22.5	20.6	500
A/2	+30	25.8	+510

Aluminium ferrocyanide sol.

Sol.	$K_4Fe(CN)_6$ added in m. equiv./litre.			
	0.10		50	100
	I	II	I	I
A	15	13.4	175	
A/2	+20	17.7	-150	

FIG. 1.
Uranium Ferrocyanide sol.

FIG. 2.
Prussian blue sol.

FIG. 3.
Copper ferrocyanide sol.

FIG. 4.
Cadmium ferrocyanide sol.

The curves in Fig. 1-5 show that in general the coagulating concentration increases with the concentration of the ferrocyanide so long as the latter is not large. At the higher concentration, the course of the curves becomes more complicated. The diluted sol is more stable, *i.e.*, it requires a higher coagulating concentration when the concentration of the ferrocyanide is low. In some cases at high concentrations it becomes less stable. The curves for the diluted sols have broadly speaking the same form as for the concentrated ones and the two curves appear to differ mainly in that one has been slightly displaced with respect to the other. The result is that if one of the curves shows a maximum, the two curves meet at same point, *e.g.*, at a concentration of 0.5 milliequivalents per litre of potassium ferrocyanide in the case of Prussian blue sol, and the stabilisation on dilution which is observed in the earlier part of the curve changes to a sensitisation on the other side of the curve. Where there is a minimum in addition to the maximum, the curves again intersect and the order is again reversed. A closer examination of the curves will show that the two curves are not parallel and the percentage change in the coagulating concentrations for every two concentrations of the ferrocyanide are different. The slopes of the curves inspite of the insufficient number of points convey the impression that the two sols while showing in the main a similarity in this behaviour also have minor differences.

The Prussian blue sol is acidic and the cadmium ferrocyanide sol is alkaline but they resemble each other in their behaviour. In the case of uranium, copper, aluminium and zinc ferrocyanide the coagulating value continually increases. Prussian blue and cadmium ferrocyanide both show a maximum followed by a minimum. The uranium and zinc ferrocyanide sols could not be coagulated with a saturated solution of potassium ferrocyanide. The diluted zinc ferrocyanide sol is more stable for the two concentrations of potassium ferrocyanide but the diluted uranium ferrocyanide sol shows a change from stabilisation to sensitisation similar to what has been observed with the others at high ferrocyanide concentration. The main interest of the preceding observation lies in that they show that the relationships are more complicated than those previously recorded. These observations help us to understand the different results observed by previous authors. Thus Ghosh and Dhar (*loc. cit.*) found in the case of Prussian blue sol a stabilisation with potassium chloride whereas a sensitisation was reported by Weiser and Nicholas (*loc. cit.*). The sol

prepared by Ghosh and Dhar was free from potassium ferrocyanide while the preparation of Weiser and Nicholas contained some free potassium ferrocyanide. Ghosh and Dhar (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1927, **31**, 187), therefore, added potassium ferrocyanide to the sol proportionate to the dilution and coagulated it with potassium chloride. But instead of a sensitisation they got a stabilisation as shown in the following table.

TABLE VI.

Sol.	$K_4Fe(CN)_6$ added in m. equiv. per litre.	The coag. conc. of KCl in m. equiv. per litre.
A	25	65.0
A/2	12.5	77.5
A/5	5	87.5

FIG. 5.

Aluminium ferrocyanide sol.

The concentration of potassium ferrocyanide used by Ghosh and Dhar (*loc. cit.*) was 25 to 5 m. equiv. per litre. It will be seen from Fig. 2 that the maximum for this sol lies between 0.05 and 0.5 m. equiv. per litre. In this region a sensitisation will be observed for the same sol if the concentration of the free ferrocyanide decreases. On the other hand, if the concentration of the free potassium ferrocyanide is above 0.5 m. equiv. per litre, then a stabilisation will take place if the ferrocyanide concentration decreases on dilution. In comparing the coagulating concentration of a diluted sol with the undiluted sol, the stabilising effect of the diminution in the concentration of the particles and the sensitisation due to a smaller interface are additional factors. The last factor has a small effect compared to the stabilisation resulting from the dilution of the ferrocyanide solution. The stabilisation observed by Ghosh and Dhar is thus to be ascribed to the high concentration of the ferrocyanide they used. It appears that the potassium ferrocyanide present in the sol of Weiser and

Nicholas contained potassium ferrocyanide between 0.5 and 0.05 m. equiv., *i. e.*, on the first ascending portion of the curve.

The comparison of the effect of dilution for the same concentration of the added potassium ferrocyanide has the advantage that one of the factors influencing the behaviour of the sol is maintained fairly constant. As has been shown above, the concentration of the stabilising ion affects the coagulating concentration of potassium ions considerably and in a complicated manner. If the amount of the ferrocyanide adsorbed by the particles is negligible compared to the total amount present, then its equilibrium concentration will be the same for both sols. If the amount adsorbed is not negligible, then also such a comparison has the advantage that the difference in the concentration of the stabilising ions for the two sols will be much smaller than what it is in the usual investigations on the effect of dilutions. The differences in the equilibrium concentration for the two sols should also decrease for as the concentration of the ferrocyanide increases, the amount adsorbed will be increasingly a smaller fraction of the total amount present. Under such circumstances the stabilising effect of the smaller concentration of the particles of the diluted sol should preponderate.

The change from stabilisation to sensitisation on dilution observed in several cases cannot be explained by the above considerations. They cannot also account for the minimum observed with the same sol. In the above discussion it has been assumed that the composition and distribution of ions in the double layer which determine the electrical condition of the particles of both sols is determined simply by the equilibrium concentration of the ferrocyanide ions. Recent measurements of cataphoretic speeds give indications of changes of a more complicated nature with dilution of a sol (Mukherjee, Raichaudhuri and Biswas, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1931, 8, 373; S. N. Mukherjee, *Kolloid Z.*, 1930, 52, 63). Solutions of potassium ferrocyanide are also slightly hydrolysed and the relative proportion of potassium to hydrogen ions associated with the adsorbed ferrocyanide ions may be different from that in the solution. Comparatively small changes in the interface can considerably affect the equilibrium distribution of free ions in the intermicellary solution even when the free electrolyte is present in high concentration. Thus variation of small amounts of silica in contact with normal potassium chloride solution alters perceptibly the hydrogen ion concentration of the supernatant liquid (Mukherjee, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 2,

191). Exact information in these aspects will be materially helpful in understanding the above observations. One of the point that emerges from the above is that it should be ascertained whether the amounts adsorbed appreciably alter the total concentration of the ferrocyanide ions. For this purpose the specific conductivity of the copper ferrocyanide sols and their ultrafiltrates and the p_H of the latter were determined. The ultrafiltrate was obtained with freshly prepared well-washed collodion membranes. A small portion of the ultrafiltrate which comes out first was not collected. The ultrafiltrate collected was a small fraction of the sol in the ultrafilter, so that its composition is not altered to a large extent as a result of the ultrafiltration. The results are given below.

TABLE VII.

Copper ferrocyanide sol.

Concentrations of $K_4Fe(CN)_6$ are given in milliequivalents per litre and specific conductivity given in mhos $\times 10^4$. Temp. = $28^\circ + 1$.

	Sol A					
	Pure sol		Contains 2.5 m.e. $K_4Fe(CN)_6$		Contains 100 m.e. $K_4Fe(CN)_6$	
	Sol.	Ultrafiltrate.	Sol.	Ultrafiltrate.	Sol.	Ultrafiltrate.
Sp. conductivity.	0.3	0.1	2.4	1.9	95.2	94.6
p_H		6.67		7.57		8.35
Sol A/4						
Sp. conductivity.	0.1	0.048	3.5	3.3	99.3	98.8
p_H		6.59		7.53		8.33
$K_4Fe(CN)_6$ solution.						
		Water.	2.5 m.e. $K_4Fe(CN)_6$	100 m.e. $K_4Fe(CN)_6$		
Sp. conductivity.		0.017	4.2		100	
p_H		6.55	7.37		7.88	

The specific conductivities for the sols containing potassium ferrocyanide are less than that of a solution of the salt having the same concentration although the sol itself has appreciable conductivity. The dilute sol is more conducting than the concentrated sol. The percentage difference between the specific conductivities of the

sols and of corresponding concentrations of the salt decreases as the concentration of the latter increases. The adsorption of the electrolyte is thus perceptible even for decinormal potassium ferrocyanide and the equilibrium concentration of the ferrocyanide is higher for the dilute sol. For the sols containing decinormal potassium ferrocyanide, the equilibrium concentration differs only slightly being about 4% as indicated by the percentage difference in the conductivity. The specific conductivities of the ultrafiltrate lend additional support to these conclusions. On account of a possible effect of Donnan equilibrium the ultrafiltrate may not have the same composition as the intermicellary liquid but it supplies useful corroborative evidence and indications of the relative composition of the intermicellary liquid. The ultrafiltrate has a higher p_H than the potassium ferrocyanide solution which may be taken to indicate that part of the ferrocyanide removed by adsorption takes with it some hydrogen ions to the interface by electrical adsorption. The amount of hydrogen ions so removed is greater than that indicated by the change in the p_H as the salt would exert a buffer effect. The ratio of hydrogen to potassium ions associated with the adsorbed ferrocyanide ions is thus greater than in a solution of potassium ferrocyanide of the same strength. These results give a clear idea of the behaviour of the sol on dilution. The displacement of the curve for the dilute sol relative to the other implies that the equilibrium concentration of the ferrocyanide of the dilute sol is throughout higher than that of the concentrated sol. The dilute sol, therefore, requires a higher coagulating concentration for its coagulation, so long as an increase of the concentration of the ferrocyanide is associated with an increase in the coagulating concentration. In this region the stabilising effect of the diminution of the concentration of the colloidal particles is added to that of a greater adsorption of the ferrocyanide ions per unit area. The dilute sol should also reach the maximum earlier as it actually does in some cases. Just after the maximum has been reached the stabilising effect of a greater separation of particles persists but increasing concentrations of the ferrocyanide decreases the coagulating concentration, but that of the undiluted sol just near the maximum of the dilute sol continues to increase. Thereafter the coagulating concentration decreases for both but at different rates depending on the differences in the slopes of the respective curves. The resulting difference in the stability overweighs the difference produced by the smaller number of collisions of particles of the dilute

sol. It is more difficult to account for the second minimum observed in some cases and the persistence of the displacement at very high concentrations where one would expect that the equilibrium concentration will be the same for both sols. The diluted sol should require a higher coagulating concentration. But the coagulating concentration for the dilute uranium ferrocyanide sol is less although the sols contain normal potassium ferrocyanide. It is difficult to assume that at such high concentrations the amount adsorbed produces a material difference in the equilibrium concentration of the ferrocyanide. Moreover, it has been already mentioned that the diluted sol shows definite differences regarding the manner in which the coagulating concentration changes with the concentration of the ferrocyanide.

The relative electrical adsorption of hydrogen and ferrocyanide ions suggest a way out of the difficulty. It has been mentioned that the ultrafiltrates are more alkaline than corresponding solutions of the ferrocyanide. The ultrafiltrate of the concentrated sol has the same (perhaps slightly higher) p_H as the dilute sol though the latter contains more free ferrocyanide ions. Higher concentrations of the ferrocyanide have higher p_H and the relative adsorption of hydrogen ion should decrease as their concentration rapidly decreases. The electrical adsorption of potassium ions being comparatively weak, the density of the free negative charge may increase inspite of the increasing concentration of potassium ions. In other words slight changes in p_H can affect the charge considerably. Measurements of cataphoretic speeds would afford useful information.

The charge of the copper ferrocyanide sol in two dilutions in presence of different amounts of potassium ferrocyanide solution was measured by the boundary method (Mukherjee, *Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1923, 103A, 102).

TABLE VIII.

The cataphoretic speed is given in cm. per sec. per unit potential gradient $\times 10^5$. Temp. = 35°.

	K ₄ Fe(CN) ₆ added in m. equiv./litre.				
	2.5	50	100	150	187
Sol 1:1	40.78	43.91	46.43	33.1	
Sol 1:7	39.07	42.02	42.19	39.36	35.65*

The cataphoretic velocity passes through a maximum for both sols and at low concentrations, the cataphoretic velocity of the dilute sol

* Coagulation commences during measurement.

is less than that of the other. The latter observation indicates that the higher equilibrium concentration of the ferrocyanide ions which should obtain for the dilute sol does not necessarily mean a greater cataphoretic velocity. At 150 milliequivalents of the ferrocyanide ion, the cataphoretic velocity of the dilute sol is greater. The measurements of cataphoretic speeds for the electrolyte mixtures corresponding to the coagulating systems are also necessary as they may bring out quite different relationships from the above. More extensive measurements are apparently necessary.

The work was carried out in the physical chemistry laboratory, Calcutta University, as a University research scholar from 1930 to 1932 but could not be continued as the writer got an employment.

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Preparation of Resorcinol Monomethyl Ether (A Correction).

BY B. B. DEY.

My attention has been drawn to certain inaccuracies of a grave character in the details of the method of preparing this substance which appeared in this Journal (1934, 11, 743; 1935, 12, 141). Resorcinol monomethyl ether is practically non-volatile in steam. The correct method is described below.

A solution of pure resorcinol (11 g.) in 10 % caustic soda (40 c.c.) was warmed to 60°-70° and treated with good shaking with pure acid-free dimethyl sulphate (12-13 g.) added in small quantities at a time. The mixture was finally heated on the boiling water-bath for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour. It was extracted, on cooling, with ether (30 c.c., 25 c.c. and 20 c.c.), the ethereal solution extracted with 10%